

NITROGEN FIXATION IN SOIL NOT WHOLLY A BACTERIAL PROCESS.

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Fixation of nitrogen may not be wholly associated with bacterial activity as has hitherto been believed but can also take place under completely sterile conditions even with silica, zinc oxide, aluminium oxide, ferric oxide, etc. when they are mixed with energy materials such as glucose and others. The energy available from the oxidation is probably responsible for such fixation in the complete absence of micro-organisms, and the reaction in light is much greater than in the dark.

In recent communication it has been shown that nitrogen fixation in the soil on the addition of energy materials is very much greater in light than in the dark, although the azotobacter and total bacterial numbers are greater in dark than in light. We have concluded from our experiments that nitrogen fixation in soils, which has hitherto been considered to be entirely a bacterial process, is markedly accelerated by light absorption and does not depend on bacteria alone.

In order to clear up the mechanism of nitrogen fixation, experiments have been carried on with surfaces other than soil and under completely sterile conditions and the results obtained are recorded in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Experiments with Oxide of Metals.

50 G. of silica, zinc oxide, ferric oxide and aluminium oxide were mixed separately with one gram of glucose and 25 c.c. of water in enamelled basins (16 cm. in diameter). One set of the basins was exposed to sunlight and the other corresponding set, covered with black cloth to exclude light, was placed side by side along with the exposed ones. Whenever the oxides were dried up 20 c.c. of water were added. Control experiments were also carried on. To start with all the oxides were analysed for their total nitrogen content and after the end of the exposure both the exposed and covered oxides were analysed. The total bacterial numbers in both the cases were also determined. In the following two cases, the zinc oxide and silica used were pure and free from nitrogen. Experiments were started on September 12, 1938 and analysed on November 1, 1938 after exposure.

The following results were obtained.

Substance.	Sunlight.		Dark.	
	Total nitrogen.	Total carbon.	Total nitrogen.	Total carbon.
Silica	0.0172%	0.2946%	0.0054%	0.5928%
Zinc oxide	0.0152	0.0268	0.0054	0.5312

More experiments were started on December 9, 1938 and the materials analysed on January 10, 1939.

Substance.	Exposed.			Dark.			
	Nitrogen		Total carbon.	* Total bacteria.	Total N.	Total C.	*Total bacteria.
	Original	Total.					
Zinc oxide	0 %	0.011 %	0.0268 %	0.16	0.0038%	0.6172 %	0.98
Aluminium oxide	0	0.0084	0.4150	0.46	0.0044	0.5824	1.98
Silica	0.016	0.028	0.3304	1.08	0.0212	0.5088	3.26
Ferric oxide	0.024	0.0336	0.4150	0.92	0.028	0.5624	2.94

* In millions per gram of oxide.

Controls analysed on January 11, 1939.

Substance.	Exposed.	Dark.
Zinc oxide	Nil	Nil
Aluminium oxide	"	"
Silica	0.0136	0.0144
Ferric oxide	0.0208	0.0224

The above results indicate that just as with soil, nitrogen fixation is possible with surfaces like the metallic oxides used which behave as active surfaces. In these cases also the nitrogen fixation is always greater in the exposed oxides than in the covered ones although the total bacterial numbers are greater in the latter than in the former.

Experiments under Sterile Conditions.

50 G. of soil were weighed into sterile quartz flasks of 500 c.c. capacity and 40 c.c. of sterile distilled water were added. They were plugged with cotton wool and then sterilised at 20 lbs. pressure for 4 hours. After the flasks were cooled 1 g. of each of the carbohydrates used was added to each of the flasks and again sterilised for 1 hour. After the sterilisation one set of the flask was exposed to sunlight and the other corresponding set was covered with black cloth to exclude light and placed side by side along with the exposed flasks. In the same way some experiments were carried in pyrex glass flasks.

In the case of silica and zinc oxide, the materials and 40 c.c. of sterile distilled water were added to the sterilised quartz flasks and sterilised for 1 hour at 20 lb. pressure. Then 1 g. of glucose was added and again sterilised for half an hour at 15 lb. pressure. In all the above experiments controls were kept. At the end of the exposure the materials present in both the exposed and covered vessels analysed simultaneously. Before analysis all the soils were tested for bacterial contamination and found to be perfectly sterile.

In the case of sterile soils the experiments were started on September 12, 1938. Soils in quartz flasks were analysed on March 1, 1939.

Analysis of the Original Soil.

Substance	Sunlight.		Dark.	
	Total N.	Total C.	Total N.	Total C.
	Total nitrogen = 0.0424%		Total carbon = 0.4305%	
Inulin	0.0464 %	0.7732 %	0.0424 %	0.9924 %
Arabinose	0.0448	0.7904	0.0424	0.9826
Fructose	0.0464	0.7635	0.0432	0.9786
Lactose	0.0456	0.7816	0.0424	0.9924
Glucose	0.0456	0.7635	0.0432	0.9562
Mannitol	0.0456	0.7732	0.0424	0.9826
Glycerol	0.0448	0.8248	0.0424	0.8968
Galactose	0.0456	0.7732	0.0424	1.0056
Maltose	0.0464	0.7735	0.0424	1.1026
Dextrin	0.0464	0.7732	0.0432	0.9826
Starch	0.0448	0.9264	0.0424	1.1206
Control	0.0408	0.3986	0.0416	0.4208

Soils in pyrex flasks were analysed on March 27, 1939.

Substance.	Exposed.		Dark.	
	Total N.	Total C.	Total N.	Total C.
Inulin	0.0456 %	0.8968 %	0.0424 %	1.1264 %
Arabinose	0.0448	0.9086	0.0424	1.0086
Fructose	0.0448	0.9156	0.0432	0.9924
Glucose	0.0448	0.8892	0.0424	0.9638
Starch	0.0432	1.1026	0.0424	1.1284
Control	0.0416	0.4208	0.0416	0.4208

Experiments with sterile silica and zinc oxide were started on January 6, 1939.

Substance.	Exposed.		Dark.	
	Analysed on May 6, 1939.		Analysed on June 13, 1939.	
	Total nitrogen.	Total carbon.	Total nitrogen.	Total carbon.
Silica	0.0082%	0.4972%	0.0038%	0.6172%
Zinc oxide	0.0060	0.3882	0.0038	0.5892

In the controls no nitrogen fixation was observed

From the results recorded above it is clear that appreciable fixation of nitrogen takes place when energy materials and sterile soil are exposed to light under perfectly sterile conditions.

It may be argued that the fixation of nitrogen can also take place in sterile soil because of the enzymes left when the soil is sterilised. But our results showing appreciable amounts of nitrogen fixation with silica and zinc oxide under completely sterile conditions dispose of the enzyme view, because no bacteria are associated with pure chemicals like silica and zinc oxide. Moreover, if nitrogen fixation were to be an enzymatic reaction, there should have been the same amount of fixation in the dark as in light, but it is not so. Again, we have to remember the fact that under the conditions the soils were sterilised, the enzymes, if any, will surely lose their activity.

It is well known that there is increase of nitrogen in a system containing a culture of pure azotobacter suspended in a medium containing calcium carbonate; small quantities of iron salts and a solution of energy material. In this case also, along with the marked increase in the number of azotobacter, a chemical reaction causing a fixation of nitrogen may take place on the surface of the calcium carbonate particles. The bacteria present in the system act as converters of energy, and that is why they help in bringing about the glucose oxidation

A part of the energy of this chemical change is actually utilised in formation of bacterial cells whilst another part is utilised in effecting the combination of nitrogen and oxygen according to the equation

There are two schools of thought regarding the mechanism of nitrogen fixation. Winogradsky and others believe that ammonium salt is the first product to be formed. As a matter of fact in culture experiments there is an increase of ammonium salt in the system in the first few days of the experiment. Moreover, in all our experiments with soils in dishes or in

fields we have observed an increase of ammonium salts within a week after the addition of energy materials like carbohydrates, glycerol, molasses, etc. There is no doubt, therefore, that ammonium salts are readily formed or they increase in the process of nitrogen fixation

It is quite possible that hydrogen and nitrogen slowly combine on the soil surface according to the equation

as in the Haber-Bosch process. There is also another way of explaining the formation of ammonium salts. The reaction involving the oxidation of energy materials liberates large amounts of energy, which is very much greater than the energy required for the decomposition of water

The atomic hydrogen formed in this reaction may readily combine with nitrogen on the surface of soil or zinc oxide or any other surface forming ammonium salts.

Another view point is that on the soil surface there is an intimate contact of nitrogen and oxygen gases and they may combine utilising the energy of the carbohydrate oxidation

As most of our experiments have been carried on under completely aerobic conditions, this mechanism may be a possible one. When the oxide of nitrogen is once formed nitrate may be easily obtained. The nitrate in its turn is readily reduced to ammonium salt in presence of carbonaceous substances. It is of considerable importance to note here that Dhar and Mukerji (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 727) discovered the formation of small amounts of amino-acids and large amounts of ammonium salts by exposing the solutions of nitrate like glucose, canesugar in presence titania as a photocatalyst and exposed to sunlight or artificial light. It is quite possible, therefore, that the nitrate, which may be produced, may lead to the formation of ammonium salts and amino-acids to be partially used up by the bacteria. Hence the presence of ammonium salts in nitrogen fixation and increase of total nitrogen is explained.

We have been able to establish in these laboratories that all energy materials can be converted into carbon dioxide and water by passing air through their solutions or suspensions when exposed to sunlight or artificial light or mixed with surface like ferrous hydroxide, manganous hydroxide, silica, etc. It appears, therefore, that in the oxidation of energy materials

at the ordinary temperature, living matter need not be associated and this transformation of energy materials causes nitrogen fixation without the presence of micro-organisms. These results seem to have an important bearing on our conceptions of bacterial processes.

C O N C L U S I O N .

When glucose is mixed with silica, zinc oxide, aluminium oxide, ferric oxide etc. and exposed to air and light, there is appreciable nitrogen fixation. The nitrogen fixation in light is greater than in the dark under comparable conditions.

When energy materials like inulin, arabinose, fructose, lactose, glucose, mannitol, glycerol, galactose, maltose, dextrin and starch are mixed with sterile soil in either quartz or pyrex glass vessels there is appreciable nitrogen fixation even under completely sterile conditions, which is greater in light than in dark and in quartz than in glass vessels under identical conditions.

With glucose mixed with silica or zinc oxide under completely sterile conditions and exposed to air and light, there is also nitrogen fixation both in light and dark, it being greater in the former condition than in the latter.

From the foregoing results it is inferred that nitrogen fixation can take place under completely sterile conditions and may not be associated with bacterial activity as has hitherto been believed and that the energy available from the oxidation of glucose or other energy materials can lead to nitrogen fixation even in the complete absence of micro-organisms.

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